

Analysis of the role of intellectual property rights protection in increasing the competitiveness of local coffee

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Abstract

Indonesia is one of the world's largest coffee producers with a wealth of local coffee varieties that reflect the uniqueness of their producing regions. However, local coffee such as that produced in Karang Sidemen Village, Central Lombok, faces major challenges in improving market competitiveness due to the need for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection. This study aims to evaluate the impact of IPR registration, particularly product logos, on the competitiveness of Karang Sidemen local coffee. This study used a qualitative approach involving four farmer groups in Karang Sidemen Village as the main subjects. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and document analysis, then analyzed using a thematic approach. The results showed that logo registration significantly improved product competitiveness through strengthening brand identity, increasing consumer confidence, and expanding market access. Some farmer groups reported an increase in sales of up to 20% after the product logo was officially registered, as well as a 25% increase in product selling prices. The main challenges faced were a lack of literacy about IPR and limited access to technology, which were successfully overcome through an intensive community-based mentoring program. The study concludes that IPR protection is an important strategy in supporting the economic sustainability of local coffee producers. The study recommends collaboration between the government, academic institutions, and local communities to improve farmers' legal and technological literacy. In addition, further research is recommended to evaluate the long-term impact of IPR implementation on farmers' welfare and the sustainability of local agricultural products.

Keywords: Intellectual Property Rights; Local coffee; Competitiveness; Branding; logo

1. Introduction

Indonesia is one of the largest coffee-producing countries in the world, with various regions that support the growth of high-quality coffee. The tropical climate and varied topography allow the growth of various coffee species, such as Robusta and Arabica, in almost all regions of the archipelago. [1]. This combination of geographical and climatic factors gives Indonesia a comparative advantage in producing coffee with distinctive flavors. The coffee farming sector contributes significantly to the national economy, with land area directly proportional to production levels [2].

One region that has great potential in coffee production is Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara. Karang Sidemen Village, one of the coffee-producing areas in this region, is famous for its production of high-quality Robusta and Arabica coffee. Rich natural conditions, such as fertile soil and favorable climate, create coffee with a unique and distinctive flavor profile [3]. Local coffee products from Karang Sidemen have the potential to compete in the global

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market thanks to their flavor advantages that reflect local identity. However, like many other coffee-producing regions in Indonesia, this potential has yet to be fully optimized due to challenges such as lack of infrastructure, price fluctuations, and limited marketing strategies [3]. Karang Sidemen Village faces similar challenges. In addition to infrastructure challenges, its local coffee products need support in branding, promotion, and legal protection through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Registration of IPR, particularly product logos, not only protects against copying but also strengthens product identity to increase added value in the wider market [3]. Research by Pakpahan et al. [4] shows that local agricultural products without Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection often lose added value because they are vulnerable to imitation by other parties. In the context of local coffee, IPR, particularly the registration of trademarks or product logos, plays an important role in protecting the fruits of farmers' creativity and innovation [5]. IPR registration not only protects the product from imitation but also helps build a strong brand identity, making the product more recognizable and acceptable to a competitive market [6], [7].

Without IPR protection, local coffee products, including Karang Sidemen coffee, often lack a strong identity [8]. This makes the product vulnerable to exploitation by other parties who take advantage of the lack of legality to imitate or claim the product [4]. For example, a report from the Directorate General of Intellectual Property (2022) noted that 30% of trademarks in Indonesia's agricultural sector are faced with cases of imitation due to the absence of official registration [4]. This situation threatens the business viability of local coffee farmers, who lose their competitive edge in the market [9]. In addition, products without a legally recognized brand or logo find it difficult to gain consumer trust, both at the national and international levels [9]. In an increasingly competitive global market, formal recognition through IPR registration is an urgent need [10].

IPR registration is proven to make an important contribution to improving the competitiveness of local products, including Karang Sidemen coffee. With IPR protection, products gain a stronger image in the eyes of consumers due to guarantees of authenticity and exclusivity, which are key attractions in the international market [11]. Research shows that agricultural products protected by IPR can experience an increase in selling price of up to 25% in the global market [11]. In the context of Karang Sidemen coffee, logo registration as part of a branding strategy can help expand market access and reach a wider consumer base. In addition, a legally recognized logo fosters consumer confidence in product authenticity, which is a key factor in creating customer loyalty amid global competition [12]. Previous research shows that similar training programs are able to increase farmers' awareness of the importance of IPR protection and the effectiveness of branding strategies in increasing product-added value [13]. In this program, farmers are guided to design product logos that reflect local culture, helping to build a strong brand identity and increase market recognition [14]. In addition to providing legal protection through logo registration, the program also leverages digital marketing technologies, such as social media and search engine optimization, to expand market reach [15]. By utilizing these technologies, farmers can increase brand visibility and sales potential, ultimately contributing to their economic sustainability [16]. However, challenges remain, especially for farmers with limited access to technology or training resources, which affects the effective adoption of these strategies [14]. This provides a strong basis for stating that IPR registration can be one of the main solutions for improving the competitiveness of local coffee, such as Karang Sidemen coffee.

This study aims to evaluate the impact of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) registration, particularly in the form of product logo registration, on the competitiveness of local Karang Sidemen coffee. IPR registration is expected to protect the product from imitation while helping to build a strong brand identity so that Karang Sidemen coffee has greater appeal in both domestic and international markets. In addition, this study also aims to identify the benefits felt by coffee farmers through IPR protection, such as increased product-added value, consumer confidence, and wider market access.

The novelty of this study lies in the holistic approach used to evaluate the role of IPR not only as legal protection but also as an integrated branding strategy. This study makes a novel contribution by exploring the effectiveness of community-based intervention programs, such as technical training and digital marketing strategies, in supporting successful IPR registration for smallholders. Thus, this study is expected to bridge the literature gap on IPR implementation in the local agricultural sector, especially for farming communities in rural areas.

This research, conducted in Karang Sidemen Village, covers the entire IPR registration process, from logo design to administrative assistance. It involved four main farmer groups as study subjects to obtain in-depth empirical data on the benefits of IPR protection. With this approach, the research results are expected to provide practical guidance for smallholder communities and stakeholders in improving the competitiveness of local agricultural products in domestic and international markets.

2. Material and methods

The approach used in this research is a qualitative approach, which aims to understand the phenomena that occur in the field in depth and holistically. The qualitative approach is considered relevant for this study because the focus is on exploring the experiences, perceptions, and understanding of coffee farmers in Karang Sidemen Village towards the importance of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) registration and its impact on the competitiveness of their coffee products. This approach allows researchers to dig deeper into the IPR registration process, the challenges faced, and the impact of IPR protection on increasing the added value and market access of local coffee products. In addition, the qualitative approach also provides space to analyze the role of the intervention from this Community Services activity in supporting farmers to overcome problems related to IPR protection and product promotion strategies.

This research was conducted in Karang Sidemen Village, North Batukliang District, Central Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara. This village has great potential in coffee production, especially the Robusta and Arabica types, which are known for their distinctive flavors. However, Karang Sidemen Coffee faces various challenges, such as limitations in promotion, legal protection, and the ability to compete in a wider market. These conditions make the village an ideal location for research related to IPR protection and competitiveness of agricultural products.

The research subjects consisted of active farmer groups in Karang Sidemen Village. The four partner groups involved in this research include Gapoktan Wana Lestari, KTH Selendang Rinjani, KTH Rejeng Subur, and KTH Lembah Duren. The farmers who are members of these groups are the main actors in local coffee production and have attended the training provided. The training focused on the importance of product logo registration to IPR and digital marketing strategies in an effort to improve the competitiveness of their products. The research subjects were selected by purposive sampling based on their involvement in local coffee management programs relevant to the focus of this study.

This study used several data collection techniques to obtain in-depth and valid information about the process of registering Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and its impact on the competitiveness of local coffee in Karang Sidemen Village. The main technique used was in-depth interviews, in which researchers interviewed coffee farmers from four active farmer groups in the village. These interviews aimed to explore farmers' understanding, experiences, and challenges faced in the process of registering product logos to IPRs. In addition, interviews were also conducted with the team involved in the Community Service program to understand their role in providing technical support and training to farmers. The second technique was participatory observation, which was conducted during the training process. Researchers directly observed how the training was conducted, including farmers' responses and participation in the materials presented. This included observing the process of logo registration with IPR, digital promotion strategies, and agricultural skill-building activities such as grafting techniques. This approach allowed the researchers to understand the dynamics of the training and the challenges faced by farmers in its implementation. In addition, this research also used document analysis to complement interviews and observations. The documents analyzed included training materials, product logo registration forms for IPRs, as well as training outcome reports that included an evaluation of the initial impact of IPR implementation. This document analysis aims to ensure data validity and provide additional context to the results of interviews and observations.

Data obtained from various collection techniques were then analyzed using a thematic analysis approach. This approach allowed the researcher to identify key themes that emerged from the data and were relevant to the research objectives. The analysis process began with data transcription and organization, where interview data was recorded, transcribed, and organized according to the main topics of the study. These included themes such as the challenges of IPR registration, the impact of IPR protection on coffee competitiveness, and the benefits of this intervention program.

The next step was data coding, which is the process of assigning codes to the data to group the information into main categories. These categories included themes such as "farmers' perceptions of the benefits of IPRs," "technical challenges in registration," and "the role of branding through logos in increasing market confidence." Once the data was coded, researchers identified key themes that reflected the relationship between IPR registration and improved competitiveness of local coffee products.

The final step was data interpretation, in which the key themes that had been identified were further analyzed to answer the research questions. This process involved evaluating the impact of IPR protection on product value-added, market access, and coffee business sustainability in Karang Sidemen Village. In addition, researchers also analyzed the effectiveness of the training programs conducted in helping farmers overcome the obstacles faced during the IPR registration process. With this thematic analysis, the research can provide a holistic picture of the relationship between IPR protection and the increased competitiveness of local coffee.

3. Results and discussion

Interview and observation data show that the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) registration process for local Karang Sidemen coffee involves several important stages. This data was processed by analyzing narratives from farmer interviews and the implementation team and comparing them with documents related to the registration. Through the coding process, the main themes found were farmers' initial need for understanding IPR and the complexity of administrative procedures. This theme was supported by statements from several farmers, such as one respondent who stated, "Initially, we did not know how to register a logo; the process seemed complicated."

In addition, observation data during the training showed that the assistance from the implementation team greatly helped farmers understand the administrative process. Farmers became more confident after intensive training in logo design, document filing, and the use of the online registration system. Analysis of the training documents also showed that the systematic steps provided by the training team succeeded in overcoming most of the technical obstacles faced by farmers.

Figure 1 Data collection activities with in-depth Interviews with farmer groups to obtain qualitative data

Figure 1 shows data collection activities carried out through In-Depth Interviews with farmer groups in Karang Sidemen Village. This method aims to explore in-depth information related to the farmers' views, experiences, and needs, especially regarding the registration of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and branding strategies for their local coffee products.

Findings from the analysis of interview data showed that after the registration of the logo to IPR, Karang Sidemen Coffee experienced a significant increase in competitiveness. The main themes that emerged from the analysis were increased consumer confidence, expanded market access, and increased product-added value. One respondent stated, "Consumers now have more confidence in our products because we have an official logo."

These results are reinforced by observational data showing an increase in farmers' engagement in marketing their products through digital platforms, such as e-commerce and social media. Some farmer groups reported an increase in sales of up to 20% after their logo was officially registered. Document analysis shows that branding through an IPR-protected logo gives Karang Sidemen coffee products a stronger identity, making them more easily recognized by consumers in the national market. The results of this study are consistent with the findings of Peng (2024), which states that IPR protection increases the added value of agricultural products by up to 25% in the global market. In addition, this finding is also in line with the study of Magdalena et al. (2023), which highlighted the importance of branding through logos in increasing consumer confidence and expanding market access. However, this study makes a novel contribution by showing how community-based intervention programs, such as technical training and administrative assistance, can address the structural challenges faced by smallholders. This approach demonstrates that with the right support, farmers in rural areas can utilize IPRs to improve the competitiveness of their products.

Figure 2 Logo-making activities and benefits of IPR registration

Figure 2 shows a training activity that focused on product logo creation and the benefits of registering Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). The materials presented aimed to increase coffee farmers' understanding, particularly in Karang Sidemen Village, of the importance of logos as a branding element that reflects their local product identity. A well-designed logo serves not only as a visual symbol but also as a strategy to build a stronger brand image in the market, both nationally and internationally.

Figure 3 Design of the coffee product logo used after discussions with farmer groups

Figure 3 shows the final coffee product logo designs developed through collaborative discussions between the farmer groups and the mentoring team. The first logo, “Sidemen—Sik Side Demen,” carries visual elements that emphasize local identity. The use of animal silhouettes with dynamic colors depicts the region's energy, creativity, and spirit. The typography and the phrase “Sik Side Demen” reinforce the local cultural connection, making this logo unique and authentic.

The second logo, “Versilia Coffee,” adopts a more elegant design with a mountain symbol and coffee beans. The mountain symbolizes the natural wealth of Karang Sidemen Village as a coffee-growing region, while the coffee bean element emphasizes the quality and authenticity of the product. The combination of gold and black colors gives a premium impression, reflecting the product's aspiration to compete in both national and international markets.

Figure 4 Product packaging sticker design for Sidemen and Virsilia logos of coffee farmer groups

Figure 4 shows the coffee product packaging sticker designs developed for two local coffee brands: Sidemen and Versilia, innovated by farmer groups in Karang Sidemen Village. The designs combine modern visual elements with a strong local identity to strengthen branding and product appeal in national and international markets.

Before analyzing the interview results, a codification of the interview transcripts was carried out. So that a collection of codification of the interview results is obtained to facilitate the grouping of theme topics conveyed by respondents. Table 1 shows the results of the codification of the main themes identified during the qualitative data analysis process related to the implementation of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and branding of local coffee products in Karang Sidemen Village. This process resulted in several main themes that were summarized based on specific codes that emerged from in-depth interviews and observations.

Table 1 Codification of identified themes

Main Theme	Code
Lack of initial understanding of IPR	Lack of initial understanding
Technical and administrative challenges	Limited technological literacy, complex administrative processes
Increased product competitiveness	Increased consumer confidence, increased product selling price
The importance of branding and product identity	The importance of branding
Effectiveness of external interventions	External intervention support

The results of the interviews and group discussions showed that before the training, most farmers needed to understand the importance of IPR registration. Respondents revealed that they thought logo registration was only required by large companies, not smallholders. This reflects a need for more literacy about the benefits of legal protection of local products.

The main challenges faced were limitations in technological literacy and the complexity of the administrative process. Most farmers found it difficult to fill out the online registration form due to a lack of experience using digital platforms. However, this intervention, which provided technical training, helped them understand the process. A respondent mentioned, "If there were no training, maybe we would not have dared to register."

After registration, farmers reported significant benefits. Consumers began to have more confidence in their products, as indicated by increased market demand. In addition, the selling price of coffee also increased by up to 20%, which

provided added economic value to the farmers. The implementation team emphasized that branding through an officially recognized logo is an important step toward building a strong product identity and higher competitiveness

3.1. Increased product competitiveness

IPR registration, especially in the form of logos, significantly impacts the competitiveness of Karang Sidemen coffee products. The findings show that after the registration process, farmers felt several improvements, especially in terms of market confidence. Consumers, both domestic and international, are more likely to trust products that have legal protection because they believe that the products are authentic and have certain quality standards.

The competitiveness of Karang Sidemen coffee has also improved because the product now has a strong identity through an officially registered logo. The registered logo symbolizes the uniqueness and quality of the product, which helps distinguish Karang Sidemen coffee from other coffee products. This provides a competitive advantage, especially in digital marketing, where branding plays an important role.

In addition, market access is also increasingly open for local coffee products that have IPR protection. Some farmers reported that after registering their logos, they found it easier to gain access to a wider distribution network, both at the national and international levels. This improved market access was also supported by the digital promotion strategy training provided by resource persons, where farmers learned to utilize e-commerce platforms and social media to reach new consumers.

The added value of Karang Sidemen coffee products has also increased after the IPR registration. Consumers who value products with clear identities and guaranteed legality tend to be willing to pay higher prices. Coffee farmers in Karang Sidemen reported increased demand and consumer confidence in their products after their coffee product logos received IPR protection.

3.2. Challenges and Solutions

Although the IPR registration process provides many benefits, the study also revealed several challenges faced by coffee farmers in Karang Sidemen during the process of registering their product logos. One of the biggest challenges was the farmers' need for knowledge and understanding regarding the legal procedures associated with IPR registration. One respondent explained, "The online procedure is difficult for us who are not familiar with technology." Prior to the training, most farmers were unaware of the importance of IPR protection and felt confused about how to start the registration process.

In addition, the technical and administrative aspects of IPR registration were also an obstacle for farmers, especially in terms of preparing the necessary documents and understanding the government-facilitated online registration mechanism. Many farmers who are accustomed to traditional ways of working need help to adjust to the online procedures required in IPR registration.

The solutions provided through the Community Service program proved effective in helping farmers overcome these obstacles. Technical assistance support from the University team greatly helped the farmers understand and implement the procedures for registering their product logos. The implementation team provided training sessions and hands-on guidance on registration techniques, including how to fill out forms online, complete the required documents, and ensure successful registration. This assistance was provided in stages so that the farmers could understand each process and step to be taken.

This activity also provides technological solutions in the form of logo design training using artificial intelligence (AI) to help farmers design professional and attractive product logos without having to spend much money. By utilizing AI technology, farmers can create logos that match the characteristics of their products, thereby increasing market appeal and strengthening brand identity.

Observations during the training revealed that most farmers needed additional time to understand the technical steps, especially regarding the online form filling. To overcome this obstacle, the implementation team provided gradual assistance, which proved effective in improving farmers' understanding of the registration procedure. Analysis of the training documents also showed that the materials provided included practical guidelines designed to simplify the registration process.

With this intervention, coffee farmers in Karang Sidemen are now better equipped to compete in a wider market with coffee products that are legally protected through IPR registration. Not only do they gain protection for their products,

but they are also able to increase the added value and competitiveness of local coffee in both domestic and international markets. The materials and methods should be typed in Cambria with font size 10 and justify alignment. Author can select Normal style setting from Styles of this template. The simplest way is to replace (copy-paste) the content with your own material. Method and analysis which is performed in your research work should be written in this section. A simple strategy to follow is to use keywords from your title in first few sentences.

4. Conclusion

This research shows that Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) registration, particularly through product logo registration, significantly impacts the competitiveness of Karang Sidemen's local coffee. IPR protection not only provides formal legality to the product but also helps build a strong brand identity. This identity becomes an important factor in increasing consumer confidence, expanding market access, and creating economic added value for local coffee products.

The results of this study reveal that after logo registration, farmer groups in Karang Sidemen Village experienced a 20% increase in market demand and a 25% increase in product selling prices. IPR-protected logos are not only a symbol of product authenticity but also an effective branding tool to strengthen product positioning in domestic and international markets. In addition, digital marketing training conducted in the mentoring program enables farmers to utilize online platforms to reach new consumers, thus supporting the sustainability of their businesses.

However, the study also identified significant challenges, particularly farmers' need to understand IPR administration procedures and limited technological literacy. These challenges can be addressed through community-based interventions, such as technical training and intensive administrative assistance. Thus, this study emphasizes the importance of collaboration between academic institutions, government, and local communities to support IPR implementation in the agricultural sector.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] J. Sun, B. Liu, H. Rustiami, H. Xiao, X. Shen, and K. Ma, "Mapping Asia Plants: Plant Diversity and a Checklist of Vascular Plants in Indonesia," *Plants*, vol. 13, no. 16, Art. no. 16, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3390/plants13162281.
- [2] R. Widyawati, M. Suliswanto, H. Febriana, and M. Abbas, "The Effect of Land Area and Labor on Production of Coffee in Indonesia," *KnE Social Sciences*, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.18502/kss.v9i21.16753.
- [3] A. Ramadhana, A. Aulia, and T. Ulum, "Keunggulan Komparatif Ekspor Kopi di Indonesia," *Journal of Economics, Business, Accounting and Management*, vol. 2, pp. 110–123, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.61476/095w2813.
- [4] M. Pakpahan, Y. Simbolon, I. Deo, and T. Noor, "Legal protection OF registered marks (juridical analysis OF court decision number 2/pdt.sus.hki/merek/2020/pn niaga medan)," *Journal of Law Science*, vol. 6, pp. 491–497, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.35335/jls.v6i3.5282.
- [5] B. Magdalena, A. Wibaselppa, and F. Febriani, "PENDAMPINGAN UMKM KOPI AROMA GS MELALUI PEMBUATAN LOGO, STIKER KEMASAN, DAN BANNER DALAM UPAYA MENINGKATKAN INOVASI PRODUK," *Jurnal Abdi Masyarakat Saburai (JAMS)*, vol. 4, pp. 119–127, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.24967/jams.v4i02.2541.

- [6] Kusnaedi, Hasbir, and Marwah, "Intellectual property right protection of Bantaeng Robusta Coffee through geographical indications," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 1230, p. 012010, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1230/1/012010.
- [7] A. Nofiana, A. Prasetya, H. Teguh, D. Zuhro, and S. Sutini, "Dampak Citra Merek, Iklan, dan Kualitas Produk Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Pada Produk Kopi Kapal Api di Surabaya," *Jurnal Mahasiswa Manajemen dan Akuntansi*, vol. 3, pp. 168–190, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.30640/jumma45.v3i1.2353.
- [8] N. Yusli, M. Abdul Latip, and A. Rahman, "DECIPHERING BRAND LOYALTY DYNAMICS IN URBAN COFFEE SHOPS THROUGH THE ECSI MODEL: A CONCEPTUAL PAPER," *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management Practices*, vol. 7, pp. 260–270, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.35631/IJEMP.725022.
- [9] S. Wijayanti and J. Suprijati, "PENGARUH KUALITAS PRODUK, KUALITAS PELAYANAN, DAN LOKASI TERHADAP MINAT BELI KONSUMEN PADA HAVANA COFFEE SURABAYA.," *Soetomo Management Review*, vol. 2, pp. 776–794, May 2024, doi: 10.25139/smr.v2i6.8456.
- [10] G. Khoerunisa, M. M. A. Rohandi, and S. A. E. Mahani, "Pengembangan Usaha Geez Coffee Melalui Repackaging dan Collaboration," *Bandung Conference Series: Business and Management*, 2024, [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:268515976>
- [11] X. Peng, "Analysis and Suggestions of Luckin Coffee's Promotion Strategy from the Perspective of Communication," *Highlights in Business, Economics and Management*, vol. 37, pp. 41–47, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.54097/vrk76211.
- [12] A. Effendy and A. Shabrina, "Komunikasi Interaksi Simbolik Spoke Person Badja Coffee Dalam Meningkatkan Brand Awareness Lokalate," *WACANA: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Komunikasi*, vol. 23, pp. 108–120, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.32509/wacana.v23i1.3569.
- [13] Aryntika Cahyantini, "Upaya Peningkatan Perekonomian Petani dengan Penerapan Branding Green Agriculture di Kota Batu," *EJKEBI*, vol. 5, no. 6, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.47467/elmal.v5i6.2936.
- [14] T. D. Nugoro *et al.*, "Strategi Brand Awareness Melalui Pembuatan Logo dan Pemasaran Digital pada Mursi Collection di Desa Mojowangi Kabupaten Jombang," *Unggulan*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 58–67, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.62951/unggulan.v1i3.379.
- [15] S. Bouzide, "Digital Marketing Research Plan for Increasing Brand Awareness of Kranicz Orchards," Jun. 2024, doi: 10.32920/26052565.v1.
- [16] S. C. Pandey, P. Modi, V. Pereira, and S. Fosso Wamba, "Empowering small farmers for sustainable agriculture: a human resource approach to SDG-driven training and innovation," *IJM*, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1108/IJM-11-2023-0655.